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Quality Management
Systems

Modern Quality Management Systems in Aerospace: An Analysis of AS9100 Standards and Implementation

Saddam Bin Matin

*Department of Polymer Engineering,
University of Miskolc.*

Quality Management Systems

Definition

AS9000 is a company-level accreditation based on the Society of Automotive Engineers' (SAE) "Aerospace Basic Quality System Standard." AS9100 has since supplanted this specification. The AS9000 standard incorporates the ISO9000 standard as well as extra standards unique to the aerospace sector. The AS9100 standard outlines the quality management system (QMS) standards that must be defined and executed by enterprises that design, develop, and manufacture aerospace goods. If the firm develops a Quality Management System that meets these requirements, it can apply for AS9100 Registration, which results in an "AS9100 Certificate." (Oschman 2019)

Types of ASD standards

According to (Oschman 2019) there are three types of ASD standards written below:

1. AS9100 – Design, Develop or Manufacture: AS9100 incorporates all the elements of ISO 9001, plus additional elements unique to the aerospace industry. An important feature of AS9100 is the inclusion of some critical elements of MIL-Q, military specifications.
2. AS9110 – Aircraft Maintenance Organizations: AS9110 was developed by the International Aerospace Quality Group (IAQG) in response to increasing demands for additional requirements that address MRO-specific concerns on safety, reliability, and airworthiness. AS9110 provides additional criteria for the maintenance and repair of private, commercial and military aircraft.
3. AS9120 – ASD Distributors of components like electronics and hardware: AS9120 was specifically designed for aerospace suppliers known as “stockist distributors” or “pass-through distributors” to the aerospace OEM’s. While AS9100 includes ISO 9001 in its entirety, AS9120 does not.

Aerospace Industry

According to Britannica, “aerospace industry, assemblage of manufacturing concerns that deal with vehicular flight within and beyond Earth’s atmosphere.”.

The aerospace industry is involved in the research, development, and manufacture of flight vehicles such as unpowered gliders and sailplanes (see gliding), uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs), lighter-than-air craft (both fixed-wing and rotary-wing; see airplane; military aircraft), missiles (see rocket and missile system), space launch vehicles, and spacecraft (crewed and uncrewed). It is also concerned with significant flight-vehicle subsystems such as propulsion and avionics (aviation electronics), as well as key support systems required for flight vehicle testing, operation, and maintenance. In addition, the industry manufactures nonaerospace items and systems that incorporate aerospace technology.

ASD Standards

To ensure customer satisfaction, aerospace sector organizations must manufacture and constantly improve safe, dependable products that meet or exceed consumer and regulatory standards. The globalization of the aircraft industry, as well as the diversity of regional/national requirements and expectations that has resulted, has hindered this goal. End-product organizations must ensure the quality of goods obtained from suppliers all over the world and at all levels of the supply chain. Suppliers and processors in the aerospace industry have the issue of supplying product to many clients with variable quality expectations and criteria. This specification (AS9100) standardizes the criteria for quality management systems in the aerospace sector (Roy, Shehab, and Cranfield University. 2009). Organizations all over the world should establish common requirements for use

at all levels of the supply chain, which should result in improved quality and safety as well as lower costs due to the elimination or reduction of organization-specific requirements and the resulting variation inherent in multiple expectations. Perhaps no other industry is as obsessed with safety as the aerospace industry. Strict quality control standards are now regarded normal in every part of the industry, as they are constantly scrutinized by the public and have minimal margin for error. In today's highly competitive global marketplace, almost all successful manufacturers, suppliers, and service providers see quality control as their primary driving force. However, independent validation is essential to establish this commitment. It is unmistakable proof that quality criteria are being met. Such certification can mean the difference between receiving new contracts and being excluded. The AS9100 standard is an internationally recognized quality system standard for the aerospace industry. The standard, known as AS9100 in North America, EN9100 in Europe, and JISQ 9100 in Japan, is strongly endorsed and followed by major aerospace manufacturers such as Boeing, Airbus, Bombardier, Pratt & Whitney, Lockheed Martin, Goodrich, Messier-Dowty, GEAE, Rolls-Royce, and others (Tomic, Spasojevic-Brkic, and Klarin 2012). AS9100 is a quality management system for the aerospace sector that is widely used and standardized. It was first released in October 1999 (Revision A) by the Society of Automotive Engineers and the European Association of Aerospace Industries as a collaborative effort of the International Aerospace Quality Group, and as such, it combines, harmonizes, and aligns the requirements outlined in ISO 9001 (Roy, Shehab, and Cranfield University. 2009). Indeed, AS9100 accreditation has already become a standard requirement for all these organizations' suppliers. AS9100, which is based on ISO 9001 criteria, places a special emphasis on quality, safety, and technology in all disciplines throughout the industry and along the whole supply chain. It applies to all domains, civil and military alike. AS9100 was created when the aerospace industry realized

that it needed to augment the ISO quality management system model to meet internal, government, and regulatory needs in the aerospace industry(Tomic, Spasojevic-Brkic, and Klarin 2012). The AS9100 standard incorporates ISO 9001 requirements as well as specific aerospace sector needs. It was the product of a worldwide effort by aerospace businesses with the shared purpose of developing a quality management system for use in the aircraft sector.(“Invotec Group; Telford Factory Receives AS9100 Rev C Quality Management Standard” 2012)

AS9100 Series

The AS9100 Standard is the first international effort to develop a quality management system standard for the aerospace sector. It demonstrates its long-term worth in use. The standard supplements ISO 9001 by addressing the aerospace industry's additional demands. AS9100 has already seen three modifications. The most recent (Revision C) was released in 2009 to accord with the ISO 9001:2008 standard. The bold, italic wording that indicates the aviation, space, and military related modifications distinguishes the ISO 9001:2008 text from the AS 9100 (2009) content. Among other benefits, AS9100 has been proved as good practice for complicated manufacturing chain and one of the crucial benefits is AS9100's contribution to more consistent verification methods and fewer verification suppliers' audits.(Gordon 2006)

AS9100 specifies essential aspects of an aircraft quality management system that must be addressed when adopting an ISO 9001-based quality system. Typically, these standards are included into robust aerospace quality systems. The industry experts who produced the standard and the representatives who approved it all believe that these enhancements are critical to ensuring the safety and quality of products, processes, and services. All quality systems must be built to

fulfill the unique requirements of their users. Moreover, while AS9100 outlines areas for improvement in the aerospace industry, system designers are encouraged to first build a strong quality system that is both effective and efficient. This system should be a holistic entity with practices spanning numerous business departments and procedures. (Hattinger 2011)

AS9100 Certification Process

Below are the 5 steps for AS9100 Certification (Gordon 2006):

1. **System scope and project planning-** In this phase industry validate of the current scope, review of all currently developed documentation and data, interview key stakeholders, and develop a project management-based plan.
2. **Documentation development and tools implementation-** The objective is to initiate the process, plan, and tool infrastructure for the QMS.
3. **Training and system implementation-** The objective of this phase is to train functional staff on the activities and artifacts/records needed to support the QMS and substantiate the system for audit.
4. **Internal audit and management review-** The objective of this phase is to objectively evaluate the QMS and engage management to improve the system.
5. **3rd party certification audit-** The objective of this phase is to prepare the industry for the 3rd party certification audit.

Figure 1 AS9100 Certification Process

Benefits of AS9100 Certification

AS 9100 is an international group effort with a goal of standardizing a Quality Management System implementation specific to the Aerospace Industry. When a company is certified to the AS 9100 standard, they can expect these benefits:

- **Operational Efficiency:** The focus on process management and improvement means that implementing AS9100 in your business can help improve your organization's efficiency. Find new ways to save money by producing more product at a lower cost.
- **Stakeholder Relationships:** If you want to improve your company's image in the eyes of your staff, customers and suppliers, demonstrating compliance with a respected industry standard is a good place to start.
- **Minimize Operational Risk:** Risk-based thinking like that required by AS9100 helps your organization develop and implement the best practices for the aerospace industry, improving process quality and product traceability to help reduce risk and improve product safety.
- **Focus on Customer Satisfaction:** Improve your relationships with your customers by offering products that consistently meet or exceed their quality expectations and are delivered promptly.
- **Improve Business Opportunities:** Access a wider range of global markets by obtaining an internationally recognized certification. Many aerospace manufacturers refuse to do business with anyone without an AS9100 certification, so obtaining one gives you access to those big names while simultaneously improving your marketability.
- **Protect Organizational Knowledge:** Knowledge is one of the most important resources to aerospace businesses, so protecting it is key. Using the requirements and guidance of AS9100, you can better safeguard your organization from information losses and simultaneously improve your organization's use of knowledge.

Figure 2 Benefits of AS9100 Certification

AS9100 Certification Challenges to Face

- **Product Safety-** Because of the high-risk nature of the aerospace and defense industries, the standard establishes severe standards for product safety, both during manufacture and in use. Companies that produce a finished product have an easier time identifying and testing the expected function of the end-product, whereas those who work at the component level have a more difficult time determining what safety means for their deliverable. These companies must examine not just their own requirements, but also the structure of their customer's product and the role their component plays in the final assembly process. They can test the function of their own product, but not how it will interact with other components. These are the unknowns that create difficulties in ensuring good product safety.

- **Configuration Management-** Companies that offer component pieces, on the other hand, frequently have a more streamlined and simple assembly process, making accurate and documented configuration management easier to ensure. This technique gets considerably more difficult for organizations that manufacture more sophisticated assembly or end products. As the number of processes in the manufacturing process grows, so do the safeguards, and measuring each activity can quickly become overwhelming. Furthermore, when firms move toward certification, these diverse processes raise the requirement for effective training and competency evaluation, which increases the required effort.
- **Counterfeit Parts-** The verification of supplied ingredients to avoid counterfeit parts a critical requirement of AS9100 is the absence of counterfeit parts. Conformity certificates are not always sufficient. Thorough testing of function prior to part acceptance assures that they will not jeopardize the performance and safety of the deliverable.

In addition to part verification, organizations are sometimes required to send samples of raw materials such as metal, lubricants, and polymers for independent composition studies. These test findings must then be checked, and firms may pay additional fees to deal with third-party testing facilities to guarantee their raw materials satisfy specifications.

Conclusion

Implementing AS9100 will encourage employees by clearly identifying their main roles and responsibilities. Cost savings can be realized through increased efficiency and productivity, as flaws in products or services are identified. Improvements can be made as a result of this, resulting in less waste, incorrect or rejected work, and fewer complaints. Customers will notice that orders are consistently met on time and to specification. AS9100 certification ensures clients that the organization has a robust Quality Management System (QMS). An organization with an effective

QMS will often outperform a company without an effective QMS in terms of meeting customer expectations. Many aerospace companies require their suppliers to be AS9100 registered. Over the years, it has been demonstrated that an AS9100-based Quality Management System leads to better operations, higher performance, and increased profitability. AS9100 incorporates all of the ISO 9001 requirements, as well as extra requirements particular to the aerospace industry. Because of the duties outlined in the AS9100 standard, firms frequently witness an increase in senior management engagement in the Quality Management System.

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